

THE ROTHSCHILD HOUSE
INTRODUCTION TO STUDIES ON
THE MOST POWERFUL FAMILY IN THE WORLD

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FOREWORD

There is a whole mystery about Judaism in the world, no one can deny that. Until recently, anyone who was not Jewish did not know that Kabbalah, a belief linked to the occult, has links and links to Judaism. The same can be said about Jewish families around the world.

The Jews had different moments in civilization, they went through times of darkness, such as slavery, as well as moments of liberation, such as the coming of Moses. They had moments of peace, between the growth of Christianity and the Crusades, when the Jews had a certain harmony with the other monotheistic religions (Christianity and Islam).

But one fact is undeniable today: the world's top leaders, be they politicians, businessmen, artists, filmmakers, musicians, and any human being who has financial power today, for the past four centuries, are Jewish or connected to Jews.

But the question to ask is: Are they really Jews? The history of the Old Testament, as in the times of Egypt, Greece and Rome, does not speak of power but of the search for one's promised land and living in peace on the precepts of one's faith.

Today the money, which is in the hands of the "Jews," bears no resemblance to the truth of classical Judaism. I put it in quotation marks, because in my understanding, as you will see below, what we have in modern reality are not "pure-blooded" Jews, but a huge group of people who converted to Judaism to keep up appearances and not suffer attacks and invasions for their crimes where they were established.

THE ROTHSCHILD HOUSE

The Lineage

Part 1

"To know who rules over you, simply find out who you are not allowed to criticize"

Andrey Carrington Hitchcock

This work is based on written literature, a study of various doctrines about the House of Rothschild or the Rothschild Family. It is not our purpose to attack or defend, but to present a study of the various versions of the theories linked to the Rothschilds.

In all the works and doctrines about the Rothschild family we don't have many files or texts before the seventeenth century, when we talk about Amschel Moses Rothschild or Bauer and what family settled in Frankfurt, Germany.

Nor did John Reeves, a supporter of the House of Rothschild and Judaism, and an assiduous combatant of offenses and attacks on Christians, not describe where the Rothschild lineage came from in his *1887 work The Rothschild Financial Rulers of Nations*. Niall Ferguson, John Coleman, M.S. King, and Count Egon Caesar Corti who dared to write about this family, none of them could tell the lineage from which they came.

This omission about the lineage of the Rothschilds makes it a mystery and even speculation about the family tree. A strangeness coming from a family, which today, is or is among the most powerful families in the world.

Andrew Carrington Hitchcock is one of the bibliographical references on the question of the lineage of the House of Rothschild. In his bestseller, *The Synagogue of Satan*, he exposed a possible lineage coming from this family.

Gordon Duff, at the Damascus Conference on terrorism in 2014, also exposed a possible lineage that resembles what Andrew wrote in his bestseller.

Between the eighth and ninth centuries, the geopolitics of the world still had the Middle Ages as its central point. The Christians were consolidating themselves as the great religion of civilization, the Muslims were growing vertically, after the appearance of Muhammad, creating a tension with the Catholic Church. The Jews were no longer as numerous as in the Roman or Egyptian era, but they had economic relations with Christians and Muslims. At this time, there was no talk of persecution of the Jews or attacks against them. It was a time of harmony of the Jews with the other monotheistic religions.

On the face of it, geopolitics at the time boiled down to the three Abrahamic religions. The vast majority of nations or peoples were bound by monotheism.

In Asia, more specifically between the Black Sea and the Caspian Sea, there was, at the time, a region, which today would be Georgia, Russia, Kazakhstan and Ukraine, known as Khazaria.

The reign of Khazaria was linked to Babylonian occultism, the ritualistic black magics of Babylonian paganism. Its king, Bulan and the entire court of the Khazarian monarchy were adherents of the occult that contrasted with the entire region. The Khazarians had no intention of converting to monotheistic religions.

King Bulan and his court, in order to maintain the black magic rituals, required human sacrifices (women and children) and his reign was known for kidnapping and murdering members of the neighboring peoples. At the same time, he stole and committed embezzlement by committing identity deception, that is, he pretended to be a person he was not so that they would not be judged for their actions.

The neighboring peoples, led by the Russians, already angered by the situation, demanded from the Khazarian monarchy that they convert to one of the monotheistic religions (Christianity, Judaism or Islam).

Bulan, clever, seeing the tension between the Christians and the Muslims and seeing that the Jews had a good relationship with both, preferred to place Judaism as the official religion of the kingdom of Khazaria.

At no time did the Khazarian monarchy cease to follow the beliefs and idolatries linked to Babylonian black magic, it only made Judaism official as the religion of Khazaria. The Khazarians retained their mother tongue, Yiddish, which contrasted with the Jewish tradition that held Hebrew as the official language.

Jewish converts from Khazaria were known as Ashkenazi or Ashkenazi Jews. They are "the non-Jewish Jews" who have converted so as not to be attacked and invaded by neighboring peoples.

At this time, a conference of nations, led by the Russians, was formed to maintain harmony among the peoples of the region and follow monotheistic beliefs. The region of Russia was a strongly Christian region.

The Khazarian monarchy, in order not to be pressured over their Babylonian occult beliefs, idolatry, Baal worship, and maintaining their black magic rituals by human sacrifices, came up with the idea of merging the occult views with Judaism by creating what is now known as the Babylonian Talmud. The Babylonian Talmud was not created at this time, it was reformed by the occult views of the Khazarians.

Despite the lure with neighboring nations, the Khazarians maintained their nefarious nature of kidnapping, murdering, and robbing neighboring peoples and were given the title of "Khazarian mafia (MK)." This "harmonious" relationship with neighboring peoples ended around 1,200 A.D.

Angered and already realizing the situation, the neighboring peoples planned the invasion of Khazaria. The Khazarian monarchy, which had many spies among the neighboring peoples, discovered the plan and fled the region with all their wealth and spread throughout Asia and Europe with other identities so as not to suffer persecution. **The Khazarians vowed revenge on the invaders led by the Christian Russians.**

The interesting thing about this doctrine presented by Andrew Carrington Hitchcock and Gordon Duff is that the persecution of Jews had a gradual growth, from this situation in Khazaria, especially in Europe, possible location of Ashkenazi Jews (non-Jewish Jews) or Khazarian mafia.

The Ashkenazis remained strong, discreet and hidden, mixed and scattered throughout the region, prospering on their riches and maintaining their occult traditions (through the Babylonian Talmud) for centuries, as Jews, and vowed revenge on the Russians and the neighboring peoples who invaded and took their homeland.

For those bravest in speculating where the Khazarian monarchy or mafia went, the speculative location is that what would now be Germany went to the Germanic region.

In what we might call the Khazarian hunt, the Jews suffered persecution all over Europe: in Germany (Cologne in 1424, Augsburg in 1438, Mangucia in 1462 and 1483 and Nuremberg in 1498), in France (1394 and 1420), in England (1,290), in Lithuania (1,495), in Belgium (1,370), in the Czech Republic (1,541), in Italy (1,492, 1,496 and 1,533), in Russia (1,891), Prussia (1,510), Portugal (1,496), Spain (1,492) and Poland (1,483), just as examples.

In England in 1290, during the reign of Edward I, the Jews were permanently expelled. They were forbidden until the deposition and execution of Charles I (Tudor-Stuart dynasty) and the seizure of power by Oliver Cromwell in the 17th century.

THE ROTHSCHILD HOUSE

"The Bauers"

Part 2

The harsh reality is that the Rothschild banking dynasty in Europe was the dominant force, both financially and politically, in the formation of the Bank of the United States.

G. Edward Griffin, The Creature from Jekyll's Island, American Opinion Publishing

The Khazarian Mafia or Khazarian nobility fled their homeland around 1,200 A.D. and settled in Europe. There they followed the teachings of Judaism created by them, which was the fusion of the Jewish Talmud and Babylonian occultism.

Until the seventeenth century, the Khazarians hid among European Jews, established themselves with new identities so as not to be executed by their persecutors, and applied and disseminated the vision of the Babylonian Talmud among the Jews, i.e., the occult.

The Khazarian mafia's next step was to modify the legislation and resistance of Europeans to Jews and to relativize and alter the view of European society towards "non-Jewish Jews."

In Germany, in the city of Frankfurt, John Reeves believes that the first Jews settled in the year 1240. Interestingly, the Khazarians fled Khazaria and its Russian-led pursuers around 1,200.

John Reeves states that the persecutions of the Jews, who settled in Frankfurt, began in 1241 when 180 of them died. In 1349, at the time of the Black Death, Jewish homes were burned down for allegedly judging the Jews for poisoning the wells and bringing disease to the region.

In the fifteenth century, still in Frankfurt, in order to avoid disputes between Jews and Christians, an area was chosen for the construction of an exclusive neighborhood for Jews, which, according to John Reeves, at the expense of the Jews themselves, and thus created the *Judengasse (Jew's Street) neighborhood*.

Until 1717, the neighborhood suffered from various situations, such as fire, expulsion (they were forbidden to enter the city for two years), restrictions and other acts against the Jewish settlement. In 1717, the neighborhood was rebuilt and expanded. In 1811 there were a little more than two thousand Jews, in *Judengasse*, in 1887 there were already fourteen thousand Jews in the neighborhood.

John Reeves, in the nineteenth century, in one of the passages of his work published in 1887, *The Rothschild Financial Rulers of Nations*, describes the *Judengasse district*, according to Goethe's description and words:

(...) No less interesting part of his description is that of the Jewish Quarter, enclosed within the walls, but isolated from the rest of the city by heavy gates and high walls. It was a neighborhood frequented by few Christians. The houses, huddled together, were packed from floor to roof with human beings living in a state of squalor and filth disconcerting description, while the air was polluted with smells so vile and strong as to drive away all but those whose sense of smell and nerves had been deadened by long residence or familiarity with the noxious atmosphere.

One of the prominent families of the *Judengasse or Judenstrasse (Jew's Street)* was the "Bauer" family, who lived there with around 550 families. According to the British Museum, the Bauers/Rothschilds settled in Frankfurt around the 16th century. In the house No. 152 and which was known as the Bauers' house and shop, it had a red shield (John Coleman says it was "red protection"), there lived Amschel Moses Bauer. Amschel lived as a dealer and trader of goods (used goods) and old coins and was a moneylender. He traveled all over the region selling his wares.

House of the Bauers/Rothschild in the Judengasse in Frankfurt:

Figure 1 - This was the Bauer/Rothschild Family Home and Shop.
This is where it all started for the current owners of the world.

The relationship with the red shield is a mystery. For Andrew Carrington, the red shield of the Bauers' house was a red plaque above the entrance door of their business and that it was a design of a red hexagram, which in the author's conception, translated geometrically and numerically as the number 666, what we know as the number of the devil. M.S. King says that the plaque displayed in the Bauers' home/shop was a Roman eagle with a red shield (from the English Red Shield, from the German Rothschild). For King, in his work *Planet Rothschild – The Forbidden History of the New World Order*, his son Mayer, after returning to Frankfurt, acquired his father's business and changed the family name to Rothschild and thus created the House of Rothschild.

John Reeves omits any analysis of the Red Shield, only as the reason for the name "Rothschild". Robin de Ruiter clarifies that the red hexagram was linked to the six-pointed Star of David in honor of the Jews of Eastern Europe, and so he changed his name to Rothschild, which means red shield. Robin de Ruiter further warns:

It is important to note that the Star of David (hexagram), also known as the "Sign of Solomon", is a symbol of magical and obscure origin. Extremely dangerous is the star enclosed within a circle. It is often said that this symbol, employed by satanic cults during ceremonies and rituals, has a deadly power.

The hexagram or Star of David is used as a symbol of the State of Israel, but it is not Jewish. Robin de Rooter clarifies that the hexagram was used in the ancient mystery religions. It was the symbol of Moloch, Astarte, and others. In fact, the hexagram was used to represent Saturn. This symbol seems to have been used by King Solomon when he apostatized, and has since been called the Seal or Sign of Solomon. Later, Jewish Kabbalism (or occultism – another name, but the same game) took it as a magical symbol. Promoted by the Kabbalah, it has become the symbol of Jewish identity, although it relates more to occult circles. The Rothschilds' use of the hexagram as a symbol of their family tells us of its implication in Jewish Kabbalism.

In the picture on the right we see the Star of David, the same star, which is supposedly linked to the flag of the State of Israel. The doctrine (when we say doctrine, we say the Occult Power) tries to create a whole vision to try to impose on society that this symbol is Jewish.

Thelema is an occult sect. For the adherents it is a religious philosophy, but in reality it is any worship or idolatry of figures linked to everything that is abject of Christianity. Today it is well regarded by the global elite and the image next to it is the symbol or hexagram of Thelema.

In this figure is the Seal of Solomon. For some, the intertwined star differs from the Star of David. It is considered an occult seal, used in witchcraft, black magic, alchemy, sorcery, and astrology. King Solomon used this hexagram to ward off evil spirits.

This is the most well-known and traditional symbol of Freemasonry. But if you interpret it more broadly, you can see two triangles and making a hexagram. Freemasonry is a secret society linked to the global elite and to various cases of rituals of dubious nature.

This rock with the Star of David-like symbol was found in what is now Iraq. We are talking about a piece from the time of Mesopotamia, of the Sumerians, between the Tigris River and Euphrates. The Sumerian civilization settled in the region around 3,000 B.C.

The symbol on the side is a symbol known to adherents of Satanism. It is a goat with horns, but the perfect alignment of the design with a hexagram is what makes the satanic symbol curious. This satanic symbol is used to evoke demonic spirits in macabre rituals.

Image of a piece from the region of the Byzantine Empire. The Byzantine Empire was a time after Christ and lasted until the Middle Ages. The capital of the empire was Constantinople, which is now Istanbul, Turkey.

Hinduism is the main religion of the region of India. India is one of the countries that most persecutes Christians. In 2024, a group of Indians broke into a Christian church service and injured 14 Christians, including children. The image on the right shows a hexagram of Hindu occultism.

Kabbalah is a mystical belief and is linked with Judaism and the occult. Next to it is a Kabbalah symbol that has a hexagram. An interlaced hexagram, similar to the Seal of Solomon.

A satanic sect called Gnostic Luciferanism, its symbology also refers to the hexagram. This sect believes that Lucifer is the symbol of Light and knowledge.

One of the symbols on the United States one-dollar bill. Above the head of the water, inside a circle are 13 stars that form a hexagram of blue.

Rotary International is a Freemasonry group. In the center of Rotary's symbol is a six-pointed hexagram that alludes to a hexagram in order to hide its true intentions.

Next to it is the Star of Renfan. The Star of Renfan refers to an occult god from Babylon. It is linked to Babylonian black magic with human sacrifice rituals. What is surprising about this hexagram is that the kingdom of Khazaria and its leaders were adepts of Babylonian black magic.

The same people and their nobles, who chose Judaism to place as their official religion so as not to suffer retaliation or attacks from their monotheistic neighbors. This symbol is the most explicit proof that present-day Judaism is linked to the occult and not to biblical Judaism (Old Testament). Literally, modern Judaism is totally dominated by the occult or Satanism.

And finally, the flag of Israel, a state created by the UN after World War II, which has always been governed by Zionist leaders, who everything indicates that they are Ashkenazi Jews. The UN is a body linked to and created by the owners of the world.

This consideration of Robin de Ruiter, and the examples of symbology surrounding the Israeli flag, makes us think about the relationship of the occultism of the Ashkenazis (non-Jewish Jews) and the fusion of

Babylonian black magic and the Jewish Talmud. That's a lot of coincidences linked to the same theme!

No, you carried the shrine of Molech, the star of your god Renphan, and the images you made to worship them. Therefore I will send them into exile beyond Babylon – Acts 7:43 (New English Bible)

In 1743, Amschel Moses Bauer married and had a son whose name was Mayer Amschel Bauer. Mayer lived in house No. 152 with his parents and three siblings until 1775. Mayer was educated and grew up to become a rabbi or teacher in the synagogue. Amschel Moses Bauer was a merchant from Frankfurt. The image below is of Mayer Amschel Bauer and later adhered to the surname Rothschild.

Figure 2 - Mayer Amschel Bauer e posterior change of surname to Rothschild.

The Bauer family was well-known among Jews in the region, although John Reeves never mentioned the surname Bauer, he exemplifies how prominent the family was among Jews:

Dr. Lewysohn states that in the Jewish Cemetery at Worms is buried Rabbi Menachem Mendel Rothschild, who was the chief rabbi of the congregation. Isaac Rothschild was director of the Frankfurt synagogue, Solomon Rothschild was chief rabbi of

Wiirzburg and Friedburg, and Boaz Rothschild was the author of a Hebrew work published in Fiirth in 1766.

Because of a smallpox epidemic in Europe in 1755, Mayer Amschel Bauer (Amschel in English is Anselm) lost his parents and went to live with relatives in the city of Fiirth (or Furth), to complete his studies, and stayed there for three years. For some reason, Mayer never liked to follow the path of theology, as he lived in a neighborhood whose central purpose was to accumulate money and it was from there that he followed the path of the monetary world. Mayer Amschel followed this path at the age of thirteen (John Reeves says it was at the age of twelve).

Mayer initially followed his father's path by collecting and trading antique coins on a small scale when he was twelve years old (1755). Faced with this ability, he dropped out of theological studies and returned to his home neighborhood in Frankfurt. With his skills in the financial sector, he was invited to work in Hanover at the Oppenheim banking firm and stayed for six years gaining experience, stability and trust from entrepreneurs.

*"One can only admire the courage it must have taken for such a young man to take such a step (Mayer was thirteen). Proceeding to Hanover, the man hoven received a small, trifling charity work at the Oppenheimer Bank House, where within six months of his arrival he was made an apprentice. It did not take him long years to conclude that the young man was successful in banking." – John Coleman in his work **The Rothschild Dynasty***

When he realized he had enough capital to start his own business, he left *Oppenheim*, and started trading in ancient currencies, precious metals, and anything that could make a profit.

Mayer moved his business to his hometown and in 1770 married Gudula (or Gudule or Gutta) Schnapper (daughter of the merchant Wolf Solomon Schnapper) and lived in the town where his father lived, in house No. 152 of

Red Shield. He had ten children by marriage to Gudula, five males and five females. All business discussions were with the sons only.

John Coleman writes in his work on the family an important fact that may be a trigger about the truth described about the ancient Rothschild lineage.

"The distribution of the financial world among the children was a favorite topic of discussion in the family (Mayer and his sons). Mayer talked about the relationship between Charlemagne and his grandchildren and how the rulers of Rome ruled the world and their view of their children. Charles (Charles or Charlemagne) the Great or Charlemagne (771-814) was a typical German, over six feet tall and a superb athlete who spoke Greek and Latin. He was King of the Franks and became the Emperor of Rome from 800 to 814 A.D. Despite his reverence for Charlemagne, Mayer Amschel swore violent hatred for all things Rome, which in older years he described as "the great enemy of Bolshevism," according to Mr. Alfred Mond in the World Battle of the Jews. Samuel Gompers, writing in the Chicago Court on May 1, 1922 said of Bolshevism in reference to Mayer Amschel Rothschild.

(...) The hatred exhibited by Mayer Amschel Rothschild could have originated from the fact that Frankfurt in the eighteenth century was a city of choice and coronation of Roman Emperors and Saints, something that infuriated Mayer Amschel Rothschild for knowing that the Catholic Church was an implacable enemy of the Bolsheviks. Some historians say that his hatred was directed towards Russia, because it was the largest Christian nation in Europe and those under several of its rulers, Jews endured much miseries and persecutions.

It is worth remembering that the Ashkenazi Jews (non-Jewish Jews) or Khazarian mafia or Khazarian nobility vowed revenge on the neighboring peoples who invaded Khazaria. It was the Russians who led the conflict with Khazaria! Yet another alarming "coincidence".

At this time, the Bauers' fortunes changed when Mayer Amschel came into contact with Lieutenant General Baron von Estorff, from the time when he worked at Oppenheim, and managed to gain his trust and was recommended to William IX, Landgrave of Hesse.

Hesse is a kingdom within present-day Germany. In the eighteenth century, Germany did not exist and had several kingdoms, one of them, that of Hesse, as shown in the figure below:

Rhein-Hesse, Starkenburg and Oberhessen were part of the Kingdom of Hesse. William had an advantage, his family was descended from the British nobility. He was the son of Princess Mary of Great Britain, who was the daughter of King George II, her grandfather.

The currency of the time in the region was the thaler and the fortune of the Elector of Hesse was 36 million thalers and after a meeting made between Mayer Asmchel, Baron Estorff and William of Hesse, Mayer became the banker of Landgrave of Hesse.

At the beginning of the nineteenth century, Europe was under the Napoleonic Wars. Napoleon Bonaparte invaded and conquered kingdom after kingdom. In 1806, Napoleon sent his army to Frankfurt and Hesse. The reason for the invasion is that Hesse used his army to support Prussia and England. William, upon learning of the invasion, fled for fear of his life. But at that time, there were no banks, as there are today. The money was physical and for the millionaire value, it was not possible to take his fortune.

Faced with this impossibility, he delegated Mayer Amschel Bauer, the future Rothschild, to hide his fortune from the French army. Although Mayer lived in Frankfurt, which would also be invaded, he accepted the risk of hiding his fortune.

The hiding place of the millionaire sum was casks of wine in the cellars and buried in his garden, both on his estate, which was violated by the French army and in the search they found not a penny of the fortune of Hesse.

From this day on, the life of the Bauer family, and future Rothschild, would change forever. Not only of the family, but of the world.

THE ROTHSCHILD HOUSE

"The Financial Reign"

Part 3

"Most people in the world do not know or examine what each person is, but rather what it appears to be. We live by the testimonies of others."

Baltasar Gracián, Spanish scholar

Since the "disappearance" of the Khazarian leaders, Jews have suffered persecution throughout Europe. They were forbidden to enter certain nations, they were confined to specific areas, they had no rights, they suffered retaliation – arson in Jewish neighborhoods, territorial expulsion and even human lynching and death.

The coincidence of this is that after the rise of the Rothschild family to power in the 19th century, the persecution turned to the Catholic Church and Christianity. The nineteenth century was known for the beginning of the placing in power any and all intellectuals, politicians or military personnel who fought against Christian doctrine. When I say power, it means strengthening the doctrine that combats Christianity, such as Nietzsche's nihilism, the Fabian Society, Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels, etc.

Today, in the 21st century, more than 250 million Christians are persecuted in every part of the world. Christian doctrine is harshly attacked gradually and reformed for the interests of the masters of the world and the occult view.

Mother Tev Cinko Filhos at Cinco Filhas, so on: Anselm Mayer Rothschild (1773-1855), Salomon Mayer Rothschild (1774-1855), Nathan Mayer Rothschild (1777-1836), Karl Mayer Rothschild (1788-1855), Jacob Mayer Rothschild (1792-1868). Enter as Mulhers Temos: Janet Rothschild (1772-1824), Isabella Rothschild (1781-1861), Babette Rothschild (1784-1869), Julie Rothschild (1790-1815) in Henriette Rothschild (1791-1866).

Landgrave of Hesse-Cassel inherited from his father a fortune from the proceeds of the British Government's hiring of his soldiers to fight the American revolutionaries. The fortune was estimated at between 30 and 40 million thalers (John Coleman says it was 40 million according to documents in the British Museum, while John Reeves says it was 36 million).

As already reported in the previous chapter, at the beginning of the nineteenth century the Napoleonic wars were taking place and the reign of Hesse-Cassel was hired by the European nations, such as England and Prussia, to fight Napoleon's army. Napoleon invades Hesse and the entire region, including the city of Frankfurt.

The Landgrave of Hesse had entrusted his fortune to Mayer Amschel Rothschild, who managed to keep the entire fortune in his house without the French army being able to find such values.

Despite the success in hiding a large fortune from a member of the European nobility, this money was, according to authors' reports, literally usurped or reused (to say the least) so that Mayer Rothschild could consolidate his fortune.

Mayer Amschel Rothschild had the support of Karl Friedrich Buderus von Carlshausen. Buderus was an official financial adviser to William I of Hesse-Cassel. They made a financial scheme that made the Rothschild family the masters of the world.

The scheme was as follows: Hesse's soldiers were hired to fight in various battles for other nations (England was the main client). These nations paid for these services. In the contract, there were additional payments for soldiers if they were injured and even for the families of dead soldiers (mercenaries) that were three times higher. Landgrave received a sign of this value. In addition, in peacetime, the contract was in force for another year.

Every year, for example, the United Kingdom hired 15,000 to 17,000 soldiers from Hesse. The money did not go into the coffers of the House of Hesse-Cassel, but was held in England for other investments. The money was reinvested as a loan to other kingdoms impoverished by wars with very high interest rates. And no soldier or family member of a dead soldier from Hesse received any money. Only Mayer Amschel Rothschild, Landgrave of Hesse and Buderus received the amounts. To maintain discretion and the path of values, the scheme was associated with the Thurn & Taxis family, whose segment was the postal sector.

The Princes of Von Thurn and Taxis (members of the Committee of 300) were very happy to have a share in the loot in exchange for acting as intelligence agents for the Landgrave, and later for the Rothschilds. They did this by so important opening mail directed, reading the contents and advising the Landgrave what they saw, and on their orders or delaying delivery of the letters for the benefit of the Landgrave and Mayer Amschel – and to the detriment of their debtors. – John Coleman – The Rothschild Dynasty.

John Reeves, a lover of the Rothschild family, in his work tries to romanticize the deeds of Mayer A. Rothschild, but what actually occurred was what Armstrong wrote:

*The suits are altogether 'less romantic.' Mayer Amschel Rothschild **embezzled the money**. This money was spoiled from its origin. It was paid to the British Government for the Landgrave for the service of its soldiers; It used to suppress the American Revolution, and soldiers were morally entitled to do so. It was first deflected by William of Hesse and then by Mayer Amschel. This twice-stolen of money **is the foundation of the Rothschild's enormous fortune**. It has since been true to its origin. There is not a dollar honestly acquired in the hundreds of billions now in possession by the*

***Rothschild family.** Instead of putting the money into wine barrels, Mayer Amschel Rothschild sent the entire sum to his son Nathan in London, and where he established in London the family's offshoot – George Armstrong – Rothschild Money Trust.*

The scheme made with the princes of Von Thurn & Taxis meant that the Rothschilds had inside information and could act to benefit from their competitors.

In one of these insider reports, one of Mayer's sons, Nathan Rothschild, invested an exorbitant sum of money in gold in the East India Company. The reason for the investment is that Nathan knew that the Company would be on a route on the Wellington peninsula. This "privilege" given to the Rothschilds made possible a range of profits for the family and strengthened the Rothschild fortune.

Mayer Rothschild made good use of his influence and friendship with Landgrave of Hesse. It was able to expand its market across the kingdoms of Europe. According to John Coleman and John Reeves, for example, the loans issued by the Rothschilds to the kingdom of Denmark amounted to ten million thalers.

Mayer Rothschild, in a planned and strategic way, and with the money he got by manipulating the members of the European nobility and, according to a good part of the doctrine, usurping the money of the European monarchy, made his sons create their own branches and offices in Europe. The locations were: London in England, Vienna in Austria, Naples in Italy, Paris in France and Berlin in Germany.

In these nations, his sons followed their father's path of manipulating European nobles as puppets and expanded the family fortune and became the most powerful family in the world.

It took only a generation of planning, intriguing and manipulating public opinion to make the Rothschilds the

greatest force and influence, not only in business in Europe, but also in the Far East and later in the United States. (John Coleman)

The political force was so gigantic that Mayer's sons obtained positions in the nobility, as in 1815 in Austria, when the monarchy granted "baron" titles to Mayer Rothschild's sons. When he could not get political influence, he bought political position, as happened in Prussia when he bought a seat on the Prussian Council of Trade.

The youngest of the family, Jakob Rothschild, was the one who ran the Paris office. In France, he established a trade related to railway lines, that is, he financed dozens of new railway lines in the country and expanded the fortune and political strength in the country.

In England, Nathan Rothschild even settled in Manchester, with one purpose: to have the hegemony of the textile industry. Most of the fabric of the English armed forces came from Manchester, but the fabric was imported from Germany. Once again, the Rothschilds knew of inside information coming from the princes of Von Thurn & Taxis, and knew that Napoleon's imminent offensive.

Knowing of Napoleon's offensive, Nathan bought the entire stock of cloth in Germany. When the war began with Napoleon, the British government had the uniforms of the armed forces manufactured and the fabric would be sold by Nathan Rothschild. Nathan was an expert insider manipulator. He had agents all over Europe and knew information before it even happened. This would be a tactic widely practiced by the New World Order, but in addition to having agents from all sectors to have privileged information, they would be the ones who would call the shots, that is, they would be the ones who would plan the future of world society.

Hillaire Belloc once says, "*Something enormous happened in 1790,*" H.G. Wells, an adherent of the New World Order, also said, "*Civilization came to an end in 1790.*" The references are related to Mayer Rothschild's sudden

financial strength that began COINCIDENTALLY, at the same time as the great European and American revolutions.

In these early years of the 19th century, the Rothschild family began an overwhelming rise to global power. Achieving situations for the Jews in the legislative sphere (rights) in order to take advantage of this, increasing the debt of the European nations to the Rothschild family as well as manipulating and privileging information to profit to the detriment of competition, society and nations.

THE ROTHSCHILD HOUSE

"To Rothschild Europe"

Chapter IV

"I know thy works, and tribulation, and poverty, (but thou art rich), and I know the blasphemy of them that call themselves Jews, and are not, but are the synagogue of Satan."

Revelation 2:9

With the French Revolution and the expansion of the Napoleonic empire across Europe, nations were destroyed and needed financial support to restore their nations. In addition, in 1815, France was ordered to pay millions of francs as compensation for its attempt at belligerent domination of Europe.

The major nations of Europe at that time needed financial support to restructure their nations. Faced with this condition, England, France, Russia, Prussia and Austria, between 1815 and 1830, needed economic loans for this purpose.

With the privileges of information, their power and influence with the politicians and nobles of Europe, to the detriment of the nations, they managed to get the major nations mentioned above to seek such loans from the Rothschild offices.

Between 1815 and 1830, the Rothschilds were simply plundering the five great powers: England, Russia, France, Austria and Prussia. Prussia borrowed £5 million at 5% interest, but received £3.5 million (70%) for its government bonds, causing the real interest rate to rise to 7%. But the bottom line was that the bonds had to be redeemed in a few years by 100%. The Rothschilds made a profit of £1.5 million (John Coleman).

In Italy, Karl Rothschild was instrumental in holding the country's revenues in pledge, much as the Naples office was courted by monarchs and political leaders for advice. He created C. M. Rothschild & Figli and also did business with the Vatican and with Pope Gregory XVI himself, who awarded Karl Rothschild the Order of St. George. The Rothschilds, according to the Jewish Encyclopedia, became the custodians of the papal treasury. In 1863, the bank was closed due to the strategic loss of the city of Naples and the unification of Italy.

In his hometown of Frankfurt, the eldest son, Amschel (Anselm) Mayer Rothschild would run the bank set up by his father, M.A. von Rothschild und Sohne. Amschel was well connected with ultra-Orthodox Jews on the European continent. Interestingly, in Germany, organized crime was full of slang in Yiddish, the mother tongue of the Khazaria region.

The peculiarity of this Rothschild office is that in 1901 it would be liquidated, as it did not have a male descendant.

In Vienna, they set up the office of S. M. von Rothschild, owned by their son Salomon Rothschild. The office's main creditor was Klemens von Metternich, an Austrian politician, who was Minister of Foreign Affairs (1809-1848). He was descended from an ancient noble family and the son of an earl.

Nathan Rothschild, in 1810, founded N.M. Rothschild & Sons. His main competitors died and he became the greatest banker in England.

I don't care if the puppet is on the throne of England to rule the empire, because the man who controls Britain's money controls the British empire, and I control Britain's money. (Nathan Rothschild)

It financed the East India Company, financed the governments of England, Prussia and Denmark. Through the Elders of Zion and a masterstroke in relation to the Battle of Waterloo, the family became the owners of the Bank of England.

In France, Mayer Rothschild's youngest son, Jakob, founded in 1810 the bank De Rothschild Frères (Rothschild Brothers), whose first job was to invest in France's railway sector.

The Rothschild family is linked to major European families, among them the Warburgs, the Oppenheimers, the Schiffs, the Sassons and the Morgans.

One of the successes of the Rothschild family and their offices was to finance both parties in European and North American conflicts. This conduct gave him important positions in the European aristocracy and important titles in the nobility of Europe.

Today, the Rothschild family has some sort of banking control of more than 150 nations worldwide, including organizations of nations such as the European Union. Just to give you an idea of how the family has power around the world, banks like the Chinese and the U.S. Federal Reserve are under the control of the family. The two largest economies in the world are under the power of the Rothschild family. Countries, which we all know with dictatorial countries, such as Cuba and Russia, and which say they do not accept "American imperialism" or liberalism are under their power.

The conflict and rivalry between the West and the East is nothing more than a means of bringing society under control so that they can maintain and expand their global dominance. Pure deception!

THE ROTHSCHILD HOUSE

"Rothschild Family Tree"

Chapter V

Lord of unlimited wealth, he prides himself on being the arbiter of peace and war, and that the credit of nations depends on his approval; its correspondents are innumerable; their courtiers surpass those of the sovereign princes and absolute sovereigns; Ministers of state are under his pay. Fundamental in the offices of continental Europe, he aspires to dominate ours.

Thomas Slingsby Duncombe, House of the Commons – 1828.

We introduce the Rothschild family and their marriages to important figures who make it clear that nothing is a coincidence, but rather an absurdly complex and strategic architecture.

This is Mayer, Amschel, Bauer and then Rothschild. As already stated, he is the son of Amschel (Anselm), Moses Bauer/Rothschild and Schonche Lechnich. He was born in Frankfurt and lived in a Jewish quarter whose house had a red symbol (shield) that was the inspiration for the surname of the Rothschild family. He is an Ashkenazi (Khazarian) or non-Jewish Jew and had five sons and five daughters: Jeannete Rothschild, Amschel Mayer Rothschild, Salomon Mayer Rothschild, Nathan Mayer Rothschild, Isabella Rothschild, Babette Rothschild, Karl Mayer Rothschild, Julie Rothschild, Henriette Rothchild, Jacob Mayer Rothschild. On his deathbed and in his will he made it clear that the offspring of the Rothschild family must marry close relatives (endogamy). Their daughters (Jeannete, Isabella, Babette, Julie, and Henriette) would marry people chosen by the family for business reasons.

It was the strategist who planned the creation of the five financial offices in the major cities of the time (London, Paris, Naples, Vienna and Frankfurt) and each of the five sons would run these offices.

Amschel Mayer von Rothschild, is the second son and eldest son of Mayer Amschel Rothschild. He was born in 1773 and died in 1855. It was M. A. Rothschild & Sohne who continued to run the Frankfurt office. He did not marry and had no children. His nephews, Anselm (Solomon's son), Mayer Karl and Wilhelm Karl (Karl's sons) took charge of the business from 1855, he was awarded as a baron, received an honour in Belgium with the Order of

Leopold and had strong ties with ultra-Orthodox Jews.

Salomon Mayer von Rothschild was born in 1774 and died in 1855. He married Caroline Stern and had two children: Anselm von Rothschild (1803–1874) and Betty von Rothschild (1805–1886). His children married relatives, Anselm married his cousin Charlotte Nathan Rothschild (daughter of Nathan Rothschild) and Betty married her uncle Jakob Rothschild. Salomon was the administrator of the family's Vienna financial branch, S. M. von Rothschild. Caroline Stern was from a Jewish family of French bankers originally

from Frankfurt. Same city as Salomon, which proves the links between Ashkenazi families. The Stern family is linked to several investment banks, especially in France. In their family tree, the Sterns are linked to English conservative politicians, British nobles and businessmen, and even to the Portuguese monarchical family. Notice that Salomon's bond was strategic, as they created ties between two Ashkenazi Jewish bankers that made Ashkenazi power greater in Europe. Salomon had a strong relationship with Austrian aristocrats, including being the first Jew to receive Austrian

citizenship, as well as being granted the title of baron with his brothers in Austria by the emperor.

Solomon Rothschild's grandchildren are: Mayer Anselm Leon (1827-1828), Caroline Julie Anselm (1830-1907), Mathilde Hannah von Rothschild (1832-1924), Sarah Luisa (1834-1924), Nathaniel Anselm (1836-1905), Ferdinand James (1839-1898), Albert Solomon (1844-1911), Alice Charlotte (1847-1922). The management of the branch in Vienna was taken over by Albert Solomon. Of those who did not marry a relative, Sarah Luisa married Baron Raymond Franchetti, the Franchetti are of Jewish origin and are one of the richest in the Mediterranean, from the eighteenth century onwards. **Minister of Public Works under Benito Mussolini.** Another Baron, Raymond Franchetti, married Louise Sarah Rothschild.

Albert Rothschild married his second cousin, Bettina Caroline de Rothschild (1858–1892), they had seven children: George Anselm Alphonse (1877–1934), Alphonse Meyer de Rothschild (1878–1942), Charlotte Esther von Rothschild (1879–1885), Ludwig Nathaniel (1882–1955), Eugène Daniel von Rothschild (1884–1976), and Oskar von Rothschild (1888–1909). Ludwig Nathaniel was married to Countess Hildegard Karoline Johanna Maria von Auersperg (the Auesperg are a noble family that dates back to the Holy Roman Empire). Eugène Daniel von Rothschild married twice to Catherine Wolf (1885-1946) and after her death to actress Jeanne Stuart.

Mathilde von Rothschild married her father's cousin Wilhelm Carl von Rothschild, and they had three children, but two survived to adulthood: Adelheid Rothschild (1853–1935) who married her cousin Edmond James de Rothschild and Minna Caroline Rothschild who married Maximilian von Goldschmidt-Rothschild, another important Jewish family. Adelheid had three children: James Armand Edmond de Rothschild (1878–1957) who married Dorothy Mathilde Pinto (Jewish activist and Cohen family), Maurice Edmond Karl de Rothschild (1881–1957) who married Noémie Halphen (1888–1968). Noémie comes from a Portuguese Jewish family, financier and competitor of the Rothschilds. And lastly, there was Miriam Caroline, Alexandrine de Rothschild. James Armand Edmond de Rothschild was a British liberal politician. Maurice Edmond Karl de Rothschild had a son

named Edmond Adolphe de Rothschild (1926-1997) and married a Bulgarian artist Veselinka Vladova Gueorguieva and then French actress Nadine Nelly Jeannette Lhopitalier and had a son named Benjamin Edmond Maurice Adolphe Henri Isaac de Rothschild (1963-2021). Benjamin married Salvadoran banker Ariane Langner and they had four children: Noémie de Rothschild, Alice de Rothschild, Eva de Rothschild, and Olivia de Rothschild.

Nathan Mayer Rothschild, was born in 1777 and died in 1836. Surely the most successful son of Mayer Amschel Rothschild and the most successful among the children. He opened a London branch, N. A. Rothschild & Sons. He achieved feats that made the Rothschild family one of the most powerful in Europe. The London office financed several British campaigns in the war against Napoleon, especially at Waterloo, whose plan gave him the opportunity to be the great master of English finances. He financed Prussia and Denmark, and helped his father in the scheme of finance with Landgrave of Hesse. He married Hannah Barent-Cohen and had seven children: Charlotte (married his cousin Anselm, son of Salomon), Lionel (married his cousin Charlotte, daughter of Karl Rothschild), Anthony (married Louise Montefiore), Nathaniel (married his cousin Charlotte, daughter of Jakob Rothschild), Hannah (married Henry FitzRoy), Mayer (married Juliana Cohen) and Louise (married his cousin Mayer Carl, son of Karl Rothschild). The "coincidence" of Nathan Mayer's marriage is that Hannah Barent-Cohen was the daughter of a wealthy Amsterdam-born merchant of Ashkenazi Jewish descent. His father had several children and they had marriages with the banker Montefiore. What is most intriguing is that Hannah's cousin, Nanette Salomons Cohen, **Karl Marx's mother**, makes it clear that Karl Marx had help from the Rothschilds in England to escape persecution in France and Prussia. He is also related to the Jewish industrialist Frederik Phillips and Gerard Phillips, founders of the famous company Phillips Electronics. Realize that if you search, the leading names in history from the 19th century to the present day will have ties in some way to the Rothschilds. Nathan's daughters had very well-arranged

marriages. His daughter Hannah married a FitzRoy who has blood ties to the British nobility (great-great-grandson of King Charles I, son of Lieutenant-General and 2nd Baron Southampton). He was Undersecretary of State and First Commissioner of Works. Hannah had two children with FitzRoy: Arthur Fitzroy and Caroline Blanche Elizabeth FitzRoy. Caroline married Sir Coutts Lindsay, a descendant of the Earl. Juliana Cohen, who married Nathan's son, is the son of Isaac Cohen, the son of Levy Barent Cohen, who is related to Nathan's wife. The surname Montefiore has been linked with the Rothschilds since Nathan's father, who is also an Italian Jew.

Nathan's grandchildren are: Leonora de Rothschild (1837-1911), Evelina de Rothschild (1839-1866), Nathan Mayer de Rothschild (1840-1915), Alfred Charles de Rothschild (1842-1918) and Leopold de Rothschild (1845-1917) – sons of Lionel Rothschild.

Of *Lionel Rothschild's* children, Nathan Mayer married his cousin Emma Louise von Rothschild (1844–1935) and they had three children: Lionel Walter Rothschild (1868–1937), Evelina Rothschild-Behrens (1873–1947) and Nathaniel Charles Rothschild (1877–1923) and who married Rózika Edle von Wertheimstein (1870–1940) who is the daughter of an Austro-Hungarian Jewish military man. Nathaniel had three children: Miriam Louisa Rothschild (1908–2005), Elizabeth Charlotte Rothschild (1909–1988), Nathaniel Mayer Victor Rothschild (1910–1990), and Kathleen Annie Pannonica Rothschild (1913–1988). Miriam Louise married a British soldier and they had six children (four biological): Mary Rozsiska (1945–2010), Charles Daniel (1948), Charlotte Teresa (1951) and Johanna Miriam (1951). Nathaniel Mayer Victor Rothschild married Barbara Judith Hutchinson (1911-1989) and they had three children: Sarah Rothschild (1934), Jacob Rothschild (1936-2024), and Miranda Rothschild (1940). He then married Teresa Georgina Mayor (1915-1996) and they had four children: Emma Rothschild (1948) and married the Hindu economist Amartya Kumar Sen, Benjamin Mayer Rothschild (1952-1952), Victoria Katherine Rothschild (1953) married the **writer Simon Gray** (1936-2008) and Amschel Rothschild (1955-1996) and married Anita Patience Guinness of the Anglo-Irish family linked to the manufacture of the famous Guinness beer. Amschel had three children: Kate Emma Rothschild Goldsmidt (1982), Alice Miranda Rothschild

(1983), and James Amschel Victor Rothschild (1985). The most interesting thing is that the wife Teresa Georgina Mayor is related to **Beatrice Webb, founder of the London School of Economics linked to the Fabian Society.** Kathleen Annie Pannonica Rothschild married French Baron Jules de Koenigswarter.

Another son of Lionel's who had children was Leopold de Rothschild. He married Marie Perugia (1862-1937). Her sister married Arthur Sassoon, a Jewish banker with ties to the Rothschild family. The Sassoon family is linked to the cotton and opium trade in China. They had three children: Lionel Nathan (1882-1942), Evelyn Aquiles (1886-1917) and Antônio Gustavo (1887-1961). Lionel Nathan married Marie Louise Eugénie Beer (1892–1975) and they had four children: Rosemary Leonora Ruth (1913–2013) who married Major Hon Denis Gomer Berry (Welsh mine owner and newspaper editor), Edmund Leopold (1916–2009), Noemi Luisa Nina (1920–2007) and David Leopold (1927–2012). Marie Louise Eugénie Beer is descended from a Berlin financier family and Belgian-German Jewish bankers called Bischoffsheim. Edmond Leopold married Elizabeth Edith Lentner (1923–1980) and they had four children: Katharine Juliette (1949) who married Marcus Agius (British financier and former chairman of the Barclays Group), Nicholas David (1951), David Lionel (1955) and Charlotte Henriette (1955). Anthony Gustav married Yvonne Lydia Louise Cahen d'Anvers (1899-1977) of the Bischoffsheim family and they had three children: Renée Louise Marie (1927-2015), Anne Sonja (1930-1971) and Evelyn Robert Adrian (1931-2022). Evelyn Robert Adrian married Jeannette Bishop (niece of Sir Stanley Hooker, jet engine engineer), after his wife was murdered he remarried Victoria Lou Schott (1949-2021) daughter of Florida real estate developer Lewis Schott and they had three children: Jessica Rothschild (1974) and married film director Sacha Gervasi; Anthony James Rothschild (1977) and married model and TV presenter Tania Strecker and David Mayer Rothschild (1978).

Brother of Lionel Rothschild, son of Nathan Rothschild and grandson of Mayer Amschel Rothschild, ***Anthony Nathan Rothschild*** married Louise Montefiore (1821–1910) and they had two children: Constance (1843–1931) who married Cyril Flower (Baron Battersea) and Annie Henriette (1844–

1926) who married the son of the 4th Earl of Hardwicke, Elliot Constantine Yorke.

Nathaniel de Rothschild, son of Nathan Rothschild, brother of Lionel and Anthony Rothschild married Charlotte de Rothschild and they had four children: Nathalie Rothschild (1843–1843), James Edouard de Rothschild (1844–1881) who married Laura Thérèse von Rothschild (1847–1931), Mayer Albert de Rothschild (1846–1850) and Arthur de Rothschild (1851–1903).

Hannah Mayer Rothschild married Henry FitzRoy (1807–1859) and they had two children: Arthur Frederic Firz Roy (1842–1858) and Caroline Blanche Elizabeth FitzRoy.

Baron ***Mayer Amschel de Rothschild***, son of Nathan Rothschild and brother of Charlotte, Hannah, Nathaniel, Anthony and Lionel, married Juliana Cohen had a daughter, Hannah Primrose (1851-1890), the Countess of Rosebery who married Archibald Primrose (5th Earl of Rosebery) and they had four children: Sybil Primrose (1879-1955), Margaret Primrose (1881-1967) who married the Earl of Crewe, Harry Primrose (1882-1974) and Neil Primrose (1882-1917).

And finally, Louise von Rothschild who married her cousin Mayer Carl von Rothschild and they had seven children: Adèle (1843-1922) who married her cousin Solomon de Rothschild; Emma Louise (1844-1935) who married Nathan Rothschild, 1st Baron Rothschild; Clementine Henrietta (1845-1865), Laura Thérèse (1847-1931), married Nathan de Rothschild; Hannah Luise von Rothschild (1850-1892); Margaretha Alexandrine (1855-1905), married Duke Antoine XI; Bertha Clara (1862–1903) married Duke Alexandre Berthier de Wagram.

Nathan Rothschild's generations are one of the most important in the family, as they are linked to the construction of the Suez Canal in Egypt, financed Cecil Rhodes for the creation of the British South Africa Company and the De Beers Diamond conglomerate. He was involved in the Balfour Declaration of the Jewish State in Palestine. Nathaniel, grandson of Lionel Rothschild, was an adviser to the governments of Edward Heath and

Margaret Thatcher. It is also linked to Soviet espionage in Cambridge. Victor Rothschild was a member of MI-5 (British Secret Service).

Karl Mayer von Rothschild (Carl or Charles, depending on the language), was born in 1788 and died in 1855. He was the administrator of the Naples branch of C. M. Rothschild & Figli. He married Adelheid Herz and had five children: Charlotte (married Lionel, son of Nathan), Mayer Carl (married Louise, also Nathan's daughter), Adolphe Carl, Wilhelm Carl and Anselm Alexander Carl. Adelheid von Rothschild is the daughter of Moses Isaac Herz (1778–1848) and granddaughter of Isaac Samsom Herz (1716–1777). They were born in Hamburg, Germany. But Moses Isaac Herz, Adelheid's father, is Adelaide Goldschmidt's brother. The Goldschmidt family is of Ashkenazi German Jewish origin and has ties to the Rothschilds. In the Goldschmidt family there are bankers, conservative politicians and philosophers. Maximilian Goldschmidt is married to the granddaughter of Karl Mayer Rothschild. To this day there is a bond between the families, as Ben Goldschmidt (born in 1980) is married to Kate Emma Rothschild (born in 1982).

Karl's grandchildren (Carl, Carl or Kalman) Mayer Rothschild: Charlotte's children have already been mentioned, as she married her cousin Lionel de Rothschild. The same can be said of Mayer Amschel, who married his cousin Louise von Rothschild, already mentioned. Wilhelm Carl von Rothschild married Mathilde Hannah von Rothschild, who we have also talked about above.

Jakob (Jacob or James) Mayer Rothchild, was born in 1792 and died in 1868. He was the one who managed the Paris branch, J. M. Rothschild & Frères. He married his niece Betty Rothschild, daughter of his brother Solomon. They had five children: Charlotte (married her cousin Nathaniel), Mayer Alphonse de Rothschild (married the daughter of Lionel Rothschild, her cousin), Gustave Samuel de Rothschild (married Cécile Anspach), Salomon James de Rothschild (married Adèle von Rothschild, daughter of her cousin Mayer Karl) and Edmond Benjamin de Rothschild (married Adelheid Rothschild, daughter of her cousin Wilhelm Karl). Jakob is linked to Frédéric Chopin, Honoré Balzac, Eugène delacroix and Heinrich Heine.

Alphonse James de Rothschild had four children: Bettina Caroline (1858–1892), Lionel James Mayer (1861–1861), Charlotte Béatrice (1864–1934), and Édouard Alphonse James (1868–1949). Charlotte Béatrice married Maurice Ephrussi (1849–1916), a banker and wheat merchant. The Ephrussi family are Ashkenazi Jews.

Édouard Alphonse James married Germaine Alice Halphen (1884-1975), daughter of the Jewish financier Émile Halphen. The Halphen family is the founder of the Halphen jewelry store, has financiers, diamond merchants, magistrates, industrialists and bankers. They had four children: Édouard Alphonse Émile Lionel de Rothschild (1906–1911), Guy Édouard Alphonse Paul de Rothschild (1909–2007), Jacqueline Rebecca Louise de Rothschild (1911–2012) and Bethsabée Louise Émilie Béatrice de Rothschild (1914–1999).

Guy Édouard Alphonse Paul de Rothschild married twice and to two baronesses, in the first marriage he had a son David René de Rothschild (1942) and in his second marriage he had a son Édouard de Rothschild (1957). David René married Princess Olimpia Anna Aldobrandini (1955) and

they had four children: Lavinia Anne Alix de Rothschild (1978); Stéphanie Anne Marie Buffévent (1977) who married Augustin de Buffévent; Alexandre Guy Francesco de Rothschild (1980) married Olivia Bordeaux-Groult; and Louise Lili Béatrice de Rothschild (1989).

Jacqueline Rebecca Louise de Rothschild married Robert Calmann-Levy and then separated and married cellist Gregor Piatigorsky and they had two sons: Jephtha Piatigorsky (1937) and Joram Piatigorsky (1940). Joram married Lona Shepley and they had two children.

Bethsabée Louise Émilie Béatrice de Rothschild was married to Donald Bloomingdale (1913–1954) of the founding family of the Bloomingdale department store in the United States and they had no children.

Gustave Samuel James de Rothschild, son of Jakob Rothschild and grandson of Mayer Amschel Rothschild. He married Cécile Anspach, who is the daughter of an official of the French Court of Cassation. They had six children: Octave de Rothschild (1860–1860); Zoé Lucie Betty de Rothschild (1863-1916) married the Belgian banker León Lambert; Aline Caroline de Rothschild (1867-1909) who married Sir Edward Albert Sassoon (1856-1912), a British businessman; Bertha Juliette de Rothschild (1870-1896); André de Rothschild (1874-1877); and Robert de Rothschild (1880-1946).

Aline Caroline de Rothschild had two children: Sir Philip Albert Gustave David Sassoon (1888–1939) and Sybil Rachel Bettie Cécile, Marchioness of Cholmondeley (1894–1989). Sybil Rachel Bettie Cécile married George Cholmondeley and they had three children: Lady Aline Caroline Cholmondeley (1916–2015), George Cholmondeley (1919–1990) and Lord John George Cholmondeley (1920–1986).

Gustave de Rothschild's last child was Robert Philippe Gustave de Rothschild (1880-1946) and he married Gabrielle Nelly Régine Beer and they had three children: Diane Cécile Alice Juliette de Rothschild (1907-1996) and was married to diplomat Anatol Muhlstein and then to Joseph Benvenuti; James Gustave Jules Alain de Rothschild (1910-1982) who was married to Maty Chauvin du Treuil; Cécile Léonie Eugénie Gudule Lucie de Rothschild

(1913-1995); and Élie Robert de Rothschild (1917-2007) who was married to Liliane Fould-Springer (the Fould family is of French Jewish origin and in the banking sector).

James Gustave Jules Alain de Rothschild had three children: Béatrice Juliette Ruth de Rothschild (1939) married Armand Angliviél de la Beaumelle and then Pierre Rosenberg; Éric de Rothschild (1940) married Maria-Beatrice Caracciolo Di Forino; and Robert de Rothschild (1947), married to Debra Elisa Cohen. Eric de Rothschild has three children.

Élie Robert de Rothschild had three children: Nathaniel de Rothschild (1946), Nelly de Rothschild (1947) and Elisabeth de Rothschild (1952).

This is Mayer Amschel Rothschild's multi-generation (at least 1st to 5th generation) family tree. You can be sure that all marriages with people outside the Rothschild surname are of Ashkenazi Jewish origin and all of them are industrialists, bankers, politicians, nobles and personalities from the history of European civilization from the eighteenth century onwards.

THE ROTHSCHILD HOUSE

"Global Analysis"

Chapter VI

One of the greatest skills of the Rothschild family is to be able to infiltrate people in the political, legal, high monarchical milieu and any other sector so that they could and can maintain their power over everything and everyone.

One of the names most closely linked to the Rothschild family is Benjamin Disraeli. Knowing that the Conservatives and the Christians had great influence in the British and English power, the Rothschilds, especially Nathan Rothschild, caused Disraeli to convert to the Christian religion, as a "spy".

Disraeli's family had a lot of connection with the Rothschilds. To German Reich Chancellor Bismarck, Disraeli was a tool of the Rothschilds and that they both had plans and strategies to dismember the United States through a Civil War.

Benjamin Disraeli is one of the great names in history who are part of the extensive list of agents of the Rothschild family. Disraeli is together with Adam Weishaupt (founder of the Bavarian Illuminati and who drafted the Protocols of Zion that would later be codified in Karl Marx's Communist Manifesto) and Albert Pike (founder of the Klu Klux Klan and a Masonic leader who has a statue in Washington).

His grandfather, also named Benjamin D'Israelita, arrived in England in 1748, according to John Coleman. He had a son named Isaac D'Israelita in 1766 and was ideologically a Bolshevik (It was the "Bolsheviks" who took power in Russia and formed the Soviet Union). Isaac had direct contact with Nathan Rothschild and his circle of power. In his translation of John Coleman's *The Rothschild Dynastic*, he describes:

Incidentally, "El-Israeli" (D'Israelite?) It is an Arabic name of Turkic origin used in the Middle East denotes

people of Jewish descent. It is likely that his father's family came from Peru to Italy and most likely, Ancona. Isaac's field was writing and he liked many researchers before him and frequented the British Museum. He was also an importer of straw hats, marble, and alum, but Isaac wanted to write.

Benjamin Disraeli followed in the footsteps of his father, Isaac, and became skilled in writing. He was born in 1804 as a Jew, including circumcised. He grew up by the beliefs of Judaism. At this time, the Jews did not yet have so much autonomy in European power. There were restrictions on Jews and it would become a disadvantage to integrate the aristocratic power of Europe.

Faced with this difficulty, the Rothschild family asked him to be baptized at the age of thirteen in 1817, so that he would have the autonomy to participate in English society and the country's politics. His role was to eliminate any barriers to the Jews in England. Here we can clearly see a peculiar characteristic of the Khazarians which, again, coincides with the actions of the Rothschild family, which is to pretend to be what they are not, in order to get what they want.

From the righteous words of John Coleman, Disraeli was the Trojan Horse of the Rothschilds in English politics to overthrow any and all rules or norms that restricted the Jews in English power.

And how this potent firm [the Rothschilds] governs the Government of France and England, similar can be joined from two recent incidents. The French Secretary of the Legation, M. Thierry, at the Dr. John Coleman Embassy in London a few months ago married a Jewess of the Rothschild clan. And now the hidden masterminds of Bonar's Law [the British Prime Minister who promised to follow Disraeli's policies] a New 'Conservative' government induced him to send as Ambassador to Paris a non-diplomatic 'Liberal,' the Marquis de Crewe, whose wife is the daughter of Hannah Rothschild, Countess of

Roseberry. Here we have the real basis of the Franco – British international understanding – 'R.F. – meaning Rothschild Freres or Rothschild Brothers'

Benjamin Disraeli was Chancellor of the Exchequer from 1866-1868 in the United Kingdom and Prime Minister of the United Kingdom from 1874 to 1880. He was a member of the British Conservative Party and destroyed what can be called the "Modern Conservative Party".

Today, in 2024, we see the legacy of destruction of the United Kingdom, to the benefit of the Rothschild family. The British financial system is intertwined in a location within London, called the "City", whose power of the Rothschilds are absolute, not even the British Crown has so much autonomy in a certain location in the main city of England. The Fabian Society managed to establish state distributism at the end of the nineteenth century (what we all know today as Social Security), civil disarmament, the legalization of abortion, the incursion of immigrants throughout the country (which extended to all of Europe, through the European Union). The United Kingdom is one of the most violent countries in Europe, the current Prime Minister of England is of Indian descent, a people of occult beliefs and one of the countries that most persecutes Christianity. These are one of the insertions into British politics and society in recent centuries, since the strengthening of the Rothschilds in England.

The Rothschilds' script from the eighteenth century to the twenty-first century is absurdly huge. They are linked in the creation of the Central Banks of England, France, Italy, Germany, Russia, and the United States. They sponsored/financed all wars (including world wars) of the eighteenth, nineteenth, twentieth and twenty-first centuries in any region of the world. French Revolution, English Revolution, American Civil War, World War I, World War 2, Russian Revolution, Vietnam War, Korean War, Cold War, Iran-Iraq War, Afghanistan War, Ukraine-Russia War, Israel-Hamas, among others.

The creation of the Soviet Union, the Chinese and Cuban Revolution. From the dictatorship of North Korea, Venezuela, Nicaragua, and any other

communist dictatorship. It is linked to right-wing parties such as the British Conservative Party and Angela Merkel's Christian Democrats of Germany. It sponsored Nazism and fascism. The United Nations Organization (and all its segments: WHO, WTO, etc.), the Federal Reserve, the Committee of 300, the Bildeberg Club, the Club of Rome, the creation of NATO, the European Union, the BRICS, all the secret services of the world (MI-5 and 6, CIA, KGB, GESTAPO, MOSSAD, etc.), financed the terrorist groups, created the State of Israel (whose leaders are all Zionists and the Khazarian mafia), is linked to the issue of Apartheid and the dictatorship of the government of Nelson Mandela (terrorist and member of the South African Communist Party), financed the creation of the Communist Party all over the world. It has financed all the nations of the world in their internal and external conflicts. He supported the Brazilian crown, the armed forces (military governments) and the communists. Funding in Brazil today is done by George Soros, the South American arm of the New World Order power. It is behind the São Paulo Forum, the American Democratic Party, it is behind all minority groups (feminisms, LGBT, abortionists, the hippie movement of the 60s, the skinhead movement in England), the creation of Rock n'roll and its specters (Heavy Metal, Punk, Grunge, etc.), Hip Hop and current POP music), fashion and entertainment, of the main media, of evolutionary technology (radio, television, internet, computer, cell phone), of modern medicine, of vaccines, of diseases and new diseases, epidemics, pandemics, etc. The hoax of environmentalism, agroecology, global warming and anarchoecology. The spread of democracy around the world as a weapon of power and not of freedom. Médecins Sans Frontières and the Red Cross. In the academic sector, it is linked to Marxism, the Fabian Society, the Frankfurt School, the Communist Parties of Europe and all over the world, the destruction of the dogmas of the Catholic Church, the persecution of Christians, the growth of occult beliefs and the dissemination of symbols linked to macabre rituals and satanic churches, that is, THERE IS NOT ANYTHING THAT YOU USE IN YOUR DAILY LIFE THAT DOES NOT HAVE A ROTHSCHILD FAMILY FINGER. Either directly or indirectly.

Both political spectrums (Right and Left, that includes this "Centre" nonsense and any other segment of these spectrums) are tied to the power

formed and maintained by the Rothschilds since the 18th century. The same is said for a leftist, who thinks Marxism is beautiful!

Ideological litigation is nothing more than a means to keep society busy with nonsense while they continue to accelerate their control over everything and everyone!

Here are some stories that are described by authors of the time whose responsibility is linked to the Rothschild family:

- Jacques François Lefranc, Augustín Barruel, Charles Louis Cadet de Gassicourt, John Robison, Sir Walter Scott were authors of the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries who exposed that the French Revolution was completely engineered by "secret societies", in particular, the Bavarian Illuminati (Adam Weshaupt) and Freemasonry who had ties to the Rothschilds.

"The great revolution has hit everyone in the world except the bankers" – Joseph Cambron, MP and member of the National Assembly Committee on Public Health

- In the Napoleonic wars, the Rothschilds financed not only the Duke of Wellington, but Napoleon Bonaparte. Rothschild agents who were at the Battle of Waterloo warned of the outcome in favor of England and Prussia. But until this result arrived in England, Nathan Rothschild speculated on the Stock Exchange selling all his shares and his agents spread rumors about Napoleon's victory, which made everyone sell their shares and reaching the minimum values, so Nathan Rothschild bought back all the shares and when the result of the battle of Waterloo arrived, He had the full power of English actions.
- A German philosopher, a member of the Bavarian Illuminati, was fleeing a police chase in France and Prussia, a son of a German Jewish banker, Heinrich Heine, helped to take refuge in England, in the Rothschild house in London. This philosopher was Karl Marx. Karl

Marx codified the Protocols of Zion, written by Adam Weishaupt, along with Friedrich Engels, into the famous Communist Manifesto. In the twentieth century, communism would be the strong arm of the New World Order, because it had at its disposal a closed territory, a dictatorship that did not allow any other country or media to know what was happening there. In the 20th century, you will realize that you have never seen films about Stalin's Soviet Union, Lenin's bloodthirsty Russian Revolution, or films about the truth about Cuban dictatorships, North Korea, or any communist dictatorship that exposes communist genocide and democide. A dictatorship would be an important weapon for the Rothschilds and the New World Order for human research (eugenics, lab-created diseases, military technology, etc.) and the application of occult rituals. The clearest example of this was COVID-19, which was created in a laboratory in Communist China with support and partnership with a laboratory in the United States. In addition, they will realize that all the ideas of communist vision disseminated in the world have a clear purpose of control over the people.

A poet of German Romanticism and also a secret member of the Carbonarios (Italian secret society), on July 12, 1842, he published a strange text with an air of prophecy in the magazine Französische Zustände, of Hamburg, in which he warned that: Communism, which has not yet appeared, but will seem powerful and will be fearless and altruistic as was thought... It will identify itself with the dictatorship of the proletariat, and although very little is said about it now... He will be the dark hero who is reserved for a large but fleeting role in modern tragedy. All you have to do is wait for the order to enter the scene. He also predicted the war between France and Prussia, which will be only the first act of the great drama, the prologue. The second act will be the European one, the universal revolution, the great duel of the dispossessed against the aristocracy of property. Then there will be no more talk about nation or religion. There will be only one

homeland, the Earth. And one faith, happiness on earth because perhaps there is only one shepherd and one flock, a free shepherd with an iron staff, and a human flock shorn and bleating uniformly (Excerpts from Heinrich Heine's article).

- The Royal Dutch Shell company, which we know from the gas stations, is financed by the Rothschild family. It was through it that they got a monopoly on American railroads, finance, and oil. To maintain their power in the United States, the Rothschild family financed the Morgan, Harriman, and Rockefeller families. You will notice that, for example, in television advertisements C6 Bank was acquired by J.P. Morgan and that the Rockefeller family is linked to the spread of Apartheid in South Africa to the world, with the purpose of freeing Nelson Mandela, so that the interests of the New World Order could follow in the African country. Nelson Mandela was a member of the South African Communist Party, was imprisoned for terrorism and became president of South Africa as a dictator, but the media and world artists linked to the New World Order disseminated and sold the image of Nelson Mandela as a hero even receiving the Nobel Peace Prize.
- The Rothschilds were an important part of the creators of the Zionist movement and the most active collaborators in the founding of the State of Israel, with Baron Edmond James de Rothschild being the sponsor of the first settlement in Palestine at Rishon-LeZion. James A. de Rothschild funded the Knesset, Israel's main political edifice. Right across the street is Israel's Supreme Court, donated by another member of the dynasty: Dorothy de Rothschild. In it you will find the Knesset and the Supreme Court of Justice, built by the Rothschilds and, after a perpendicular line, several blocks away, is the Rockefeller Museum (another Jewish and Masonic family). In 1917, Walter Rothschild, 2nd Baron Rothschild, was the recipient of the Balfour Declaration, which established the settlement of Palestine by the British government as the homeland of the Jews. It is good to remember that the Bible talks about the State of Israel for God's chosen people, the true Jews. It was the Rothschilds and their agents (UN) who created the State of Israel through a decades-old ploy. The

problem is that with Adolf Hitler's major role in eliminating all true Jews, the New World Order has achieved that the majority of Jews in the world (almost 90%) are either non-Jewish Jews (Ashkenazis – Khazarian mafia) or Jewish Zionism. All the leaders of the State of Israel, no matter what spectrum or party, are Zionists. The Mossad is their armed wing.

- Walter Rothschild, 2nd Baron Rothschild, was the recipient of the Balfour Declaration to the Zionist Federation, which committed the British government to the establishment in Palestine of a national home for the Jewish people. **Lord Victor Rothschild was against granting asylum or even aid to Jewish refugees during the Nazi holocaust.** Walter and Victor's actions only demonstrate that they wanted to maintain the extermination of the real Jews, so that they would make the Ashkenazis (non-Jews) the only members of modern Judaism.
- Mikhail Bakunin, one of the co-founders of the First Communist International with Marx and Proudhon in 1842, as well as one of the servants of anarcho-communism when he wrote a letter to the communists of Bologna in 1871: "*Well, this whole Jewish world which forms a single exploitative sect, a kind of leech of the people, a devouring and organized collective parasite, not only across the borders of the states, but through all the differences of opinion. This world is currently, at least to a large extent, at the disposal of Marx on the one hand and the Rothschilds on the other. I know that the Rothschilds, as reactionaries that they are and should be, greatly appreciate the merits of the Communist Marx, and in turn the Communist Marx is inevitably attracted, by an instinctive attraction and a respectful admiration, in the direction of the Rothschilds' financial genius. Jewish solidarity, this strong solidarity that has been maintained throughout history, unites them.*"
- Another "coincidence" about the Ashkenazis and Russia comes from Gustavo Barroso's work on the Protocols of the Elders of Zion. It is good to remember that the Ashkenazis swore vengeance on the Christian Russian people. In the First Part of Gustavo Barroso's work – The Jewish Danger by Roger Lambelin he translates:

- *The Russian writer G. Butmi published a version of this text in 1907, with the help of his brother A. L. Butmi, under the title: "The Enemies of Mankind" (5). Printed by the St. Petersburg Institute for Deaf and Dumb Persons, the book was dedicated to the Russian People's Union, a patriotic association **that fought the Jews and the secret societies, which were very numerous in the tsar's empire. (...) The 1917 edition was almost completely destroyed by the Bolsheviks.** It is good to remember that the Czars fought the Rothschilds, Lenin, Trotsky and Stalin received financial support from the Ashkenazi bankers, in a meeting held in Switzerland in 1906, when they tried the first Revolution and it did not work, but in 1917 they succeeded. The Protocols are proof of the actions of the New World Order and the Bolsheviks destroyed it, why this action? Trotsky and Lenin were Jews, they were financed by Ashkenazi Jews, the rest of the story you know! The Tsars were deposed and the whole family was murdered, Russia became the Soviet Union, a bloodthirsty and merciless and totally closed government, everything the Ashkenazis needed to maintain their power and their human research. Finally, **in a circular of the Zionist Commission in 1901, in which Dr. Teodoro Hertzl complains about the disappearance of papers that allowed Christians to know the secrets of the "Protocols".***

THE ROTHSCHILD HOUSE

"Conclusive Analysis"

Chapter VII

There are two stories: the official and lying history that is taught ad usum delphini (inadequate teaching), and the secret history, in which you will find the truth and its true causes, that is, a shameful history.

Honoré de Balzac

This article should not be read for the purpose of hating the Jewish people, on the contrary, it has the scope of separating the true Jewish people from those who pose as Jews in order to dominate the world.

"Judaism is the enigma of modern times, the enigma that must be deciphered, after all, at the crossroads. Hitherto they have been obstinate in judging Judaism by the positive or speculative activity of the Jews. Bad method meant for disappointments. The Jews! But they have a share in all material and spiritual enterprises, in all resistances and in all revolts. . . . (A. de Monzie, preface to Kadmi-Cohen: Nomads, p. X) of Gustavo Barroso's Protocols of the Elders of Zion.

Jesus Christ was a Jew, God's chosen people are the Jews. The problem is that a certain group that has imposed itself as Jews and in reality is not, speaks for the Jewish religion and has changed the dogmatics of the Jewish religion!

Today the majority of Jews are Ashkenazis, for the simple fact that the Ashkenazis engineer the extinction of the true Jewish people and everything that is linked to the Judaism of the Holy Bible must be destroyed, including the continuity of its son, that is, Christianity.

Don't you wonder why the money is in the hands of the "Jews"? And why not follow the teachings of Moses, for example? Why do they prefer to destroy everyone and not follow the path of heavenly peace? Why was the State of Israel voted and approved by an organization that is under the power of a few Jews and instead of keeping the region in peace prefers to keep the region in constant tension?

Why was Russia chosen to go through a Bolshevik revolution? Remember the Ashkenazis' promise of revenge on the Russian people? Remember Mayer Amschel Rothschild told his children about Russia and Christians? Christians, who have been persecuted for three hundred years. In the 21st century, more than 250 million Christians are persecuted around the world.

Isn't it much of a coincidence that you have a flag of a state linked to Judaism and you have an occult and pagan star, which is even linked to the Babylonian occultism that was the belief of the people of Khazaria?

Isn't it too much of a coincidence that in the Frankfurt region a certain supposedly Jewish family kept the same symbols of a pagan/occult religion?

There are many coincidences that are linked to this family, which today and for three hundred years, are the masters of the world. They are behind all the geopolitical events in the world. All international organizations, armies and wars, secret services and espionage, politicians, banking and financial systems, technology, entertainment, secret societies and religions.

The reality is that God's chosen people (the true Jews) are being decimated, Christians are being annihilated from the planet, and more and more pagan programs and ideologues are perfecting themselves and immersing society in their beliefs.

If you think about it, in Christian countries, you see fewer and fewer believers in the churches. Christians who have never read the Bible. They don't know the history of Christianity, of Jesus Christ, they don't know how to pray the Lord's Prayer or Hail Mary. Because? Is this something natural

or architected? It's only an idiot to think that's natural! Today people would rather watch a science fiction movie than pray. This is not natural, it was built.

The modern "naturalness" of today is the architecture of yesterday. They are the fruits of the plantation of three hundred years ago. Do you think the war between Ukraine and Russia is a natural thing? Or Hamas's war with Israel? Or the appearance of groups on feminism, sexuality and gender? The legalization of drugs, civil disarmament, terrorism, the mysterious deaths that occur to some people around the world, the technology sold to society, the vaccine created for a certain disease, the creation of international organizations, the formation of international foundations, financial systems, and economic crises. All of these examples are global constructs for an inert and ignorant society.

It's being so immersed in the problem that you don't have the strength to look for the right path. It is to understand the way, but prefers to look at the problem and omit it. A real coward. Society is increasingly like this, thinking that pursuing your own personal successes will give you peace of mind! You are wrong!

In short, society is drowning in the materiality of this life and forgets the later plane. They have forgotten where they came from and who will really judge them. Materialism is only a passage, but the soul is immortal.

REFERENCES:

- ARMSTRONG, George Washington. The Rothschild Money Trust. He was an American judge.
- BALLA, Ignatius. The Romance of the Rothschilds. London: Legislative Library: 1913;
- BARROSO, Gustavo. *The Protocols of the Elders of Zion – The Imperialism of Israel. The Jews' Plan for the Conquest of the World. The Antichrist Code. Proof of authenticity, documents, notes and comments.* Agência Minerva Editora: São Paulo, 1936. p. 15;
- BORREGO, Salvador. Economic weapon. Editorial Casa de Tharsis, 2000;
- CARR, William Guy. *Pawns in the Game.* He was a navigational officer in World War I, Naval control officer of the St. Lawrence and Staff Operations Officer at Shelbourne N.S. As an author he published seven works, some of which were destined for The Royal Library, the Imperial War Museum Library and the Millington Drake Library;
- CARR, William Guy. *Satan, Prince of this World.* 1966;
- CERESOLE, Norberto. The Falsification of Reality: Geopolitical Space of Jewish Terrorism. La Editorial: La Paz, 2018;
- COLEMAN, John. *The Rothschild Dynasty.* Ed. Omnia Veritas, 2023. John Coleman is a British author and former member of the secret intelligence service;
- CORTI, Egon Caesar Count. *The Rise the House of Rothschild.* Insel-Verlag, Leipzig, 1927. Croatian was an Austrian official, historian and writer.
- DE RUITER, Robin. *The Antichrist – Hidden Power Behind the New World Order.* LeLivros, 2013; Born in the Netherlands, Robin de Ruiten studied theology, history and Spanish. Helped people with psychological trauma who have experienced satanic ritual abuse;
- DORSEY III, Herbert G. *The Secret History of the New World Order.* Outskirts Press: 2014. He received a bachelor's degree in electrical engineering from the University of California at Santa Barbara in 1982;
- ESTULIN, Daniel. The True Story of the Bilderberg Club. Editorial Planeta: 2005

- GRAZIANO, Walter. Hitler Won the War: The Economic Power and Game of Interests Behind International Relations. São Paulo: Editora Palindromo, 2005;
- HELSING, Jan Van. Secret Societies and Their Power in the 20th Century. Ewertverlag: 1998;
- HITCHCOCK, Andrew Carrington. *The Synagogue of Satan*. 2007; Historiador, pastor e satírico americano;
- KING, M.S. *Planet Rothschild – Vol. 1, 2 and 3 – The Forbidden History of the New World Order*. 2015. She is a private investigative journalist and researcher in the City of York. He graduated in 1987 from Rutgers University;
- KOCH, Paul H. The Hidden History of the World: From Prehistory to International Terraticism. FreCos, 2007;
- MARSDEN, Victor E. *Protocols of the Learned Elders of Zion*. Translated from the Russian of Nilus. The Mercian Free Press: England, 2014;
- NIALL, Ferguson. *The House of Rothschild – The World's Banker*. Penguin Books, 1998. Born in Glasgow in 1964, he is a Tutor in Modern History at Jesus College, Oxford and a political scientist.
- QUIGLEY, Carroll. *Tragedy & Hope: The History of the World in Out Time*. 2004;
- REEVES, John. *The Rothschilds: The Financial Rulers of Nations*. Chicago: A.C.McClurg, 1887;
- ROBISON, John. Proofs of a Conspiracy Against all the Religions and Governments of Europe. 3ª Edição, 1798.

SITES SEARCHED:

- <https://archive.org/create/>
- <https://web.archive.org/>
- <https://www.rothschildarchive.org/>
- <https://www.jewishvirtuallibrary.org/the-rothschild-archive>
- <https://archive.jisk.ac.uk/search/location/8a0def45-90d7-3a8d-8673-2423c5918d5c>
- <https://Discovery.Nationalarchives.gov.uk/details/A/A13533137>
- https://pt.wikipedia.org/wiki/Wikip%C3%A9dia:P%C3%A1gina_principal
- <https://pt.scribd.com/Home>
- <https://www.bodleian.ox.ac.uk/universityarchives>
- <https://dokeru.com/>
- <https://www.marxists.org/portugues/bakunin/1871/mes/carta16.htm>

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